

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The level of education and literacy of the people plays an important role in the development and economic progress of the country. The advancements in technology and its adoption brings with it a more productive, profitable, and efficient future. This has led to computer technology being incorporated into almost any area. The potential of higher education in the coming years is linked with developments of new technologies and the efficiency of emerging intelligence machines. Artificial Intelligence is currently dominating various fields such as finance, marketing, social media, healthcare, and education etc. Educational tools with AI features have garnered attention for their potential to improve quality of education and enhance the present method of teaching and learning. AI caters to the needs and learning abilities of the learner. This paper studies the influence of artificial intelligence in imparting education.

Keywords: *Education, Technology, Artificial intelligence, Chabot*

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Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence is a collection of technologies that are capable of sensing, reasoning and behaving like human beings. AI uses Knowledge and techniques from fields like Mathematics, Statistics, Biology and domain-specific expertise to create models, software programs and tools which can undertake complex problems. An Artificial Intelligent system learns from experience, it uses large amount of data to develop a methodology and identifies patterns in the data to solve complex problems, it can understand languages and its distinctions and creates perspectives. We observe the use of AI in all segments of society through its most common applications like chatbots,

biometric systems, and recommendations engines and targeted marketing. AI complements and supplements human intelligence and thereby enriches the way people carry out day to day activities. This is possible due to the underlying intelligent machines which permit high-level cognitive processes like solving problems, making decisions, and learning which in turn is possible due to improvements in data collection, processing speed, aggregation, and analytics. These high-level machine learning algorithms respond in real-time. Advancements in technology and automation at workplace will affect the job sector. In a study conducted by EY and NASSCOM it is predicted that by 2022, around 46% of the workforce will be engaged in entirely new jobs that do not exist today or will be employed in jobs that have completely changed skillsets. Major Tech companies like Apple, Google, and Microsoft are investing in AI research. It is necessary to train future generations to develop future talent in accordance with the changing needs of job market. When AI is used in education sector it will change the way we learn, it can help the students by giving information of the college and the facility available to them, determine the best teaching methods, for each student as per their needs and addressing them, this will help him to get better grades and skillsets. AI helps to automate and speed up administrative tasks. Intelligent learning systems (ITS) can function without the teacher being present and support, engage the learners. It can analyse patterns and give students efficient study schedule.

Literature Review

There has been an increase in the application of AI to the education sector. According to the Horizon report (Educause, 2018), the adoption of AI to education is one of the most important developments in recent years. Faculty, staff, and students must understand the connection between tools and the outcomes leveraging technology in creative ways that allow them to easily adapt from one context to another. As argued by Malone (2018) AI systems can enhance human intelligence acting as ‘superminds’. To adopt AI a mutual understanding between the key stakeholders of AI technologies including public, educators and academia needs to exist (Cukurova et al.2019). In fact, Nick Bostrom, Director, Future of Humanity Institute at UK’s Oxford University has observed that since 2006 AI is an integral part of our daily life, it has become so common that we no longer distinguish it amongst the new applications (Bostrom 2006). Students are exposed to lot of opportunities and challenges for learning and teaching in higher education. Technological solutions are already available to help people with disabilities. They can

inspire educators to apply them in education to augment learners and teachers for a more engaging process (Popenci S, Kerr S 2017).

Objective

To study the area's where AI can help in improving the quality and accessibility of education.

Methodology

This research is based on secondary data collected from various publications, articles, reports, and websites.

Need for AI in Indian Education System

India has the world's largest population of about 310 million in the age group of 6 to 17 attending school, another working population around 520 million in the age group of 25 to 59, that is every third person in India is a youth who has the potential to advance the economy of the country. In the 2016 statistics report put forth by the Human Resource & Development Ministry, there is a shortage of 1 million teachers across the country in the higher education sector. In addition to this, there is a shortage of qualified teachers to fill these positions. The Indian education system needs technological intervention which can make it more accessible and affordable. Bringing Artificial Intelligence to classrooms in India might just be the solution that we have been looking for. AI-enabled tools such as robots monitor performance of individual students based on their previous performance, help in identifying their problem areas and offer recommendations just like a teacher; also, AI provides customized content to cater to the needs of the student. Using AI technique we can reduce the gap between urban and rural education. According to a report by NITI Ayog if AI is used efficiently it has the power to transform the Indian education sector. Given the population of India, a lot of data can be collected which can be made readily available. This data forms the basis to train these AI agents using state of the art Machine learning algorithms coupled with massive computing power.

Implications of AI in Education

Here are just a few of the ways AI tools, and those that will follow them will shape and define the educational sector of the future.

Translation Systems

Real-time text to speech and text translation systems can be used to distribute information flawlessly in the regional language. The language barrier could be removed and the interoperability of teachers across states can be achieved.

Attendance

Biometric authentication can help in taking attendance of the students and these attendance records can be used to monitor the student's regularity in the course.

Chatbot

A chatbot is a computer program that engages the user in conversation either through text or speech. These Chatbots can be used to give information regarding courses and the facility available in college. It can be trained on subject matter and used to clear the doubts of the students. The following table gives the Chatbots used in the education field

Chatbot Name	Purpose
Botsify	Education: Presents a specific topic to the students in the form of text, images, videos, and a combination of these.
Snatchbot	Education: It can be used by teachers to aid their teaching.
Jill Watson- Georgia Tech university	Teaching Assistant: The bot answers student's questions on an online forum and provides technical information's about courses and lectures.
CourseQ	To communicate: The college group can use it to broadcast messages and answer student's queries. Teachers can use it to ask questions and solve student's problems.
Hubert	Feedback: This bot interacts with students and receives the feedback regarding course, the bot then analyzes the feedback, compiles the highlighted points mentioned by the majority of students and then sends it to the teacher.
Pounce- Georgia state University	A custom virtual assistant for GSU admissions. It helps students by sending timely reminders and information about admission tasks, collects survey data. Answers student's questions round the clock.
Genie-Deakin University	A voice-controlled smartphone app: Answers all the queries 24/7 and ensure you feel supported, organized and in control throughout your studies

Content Creation

Given the huge amount of information available on the internet, Automatic text summarization to create content can be done using NLP techniques and publish them on the e-learning websites.

Voice assistants such as Amazon Alexa, Google Home, Apple Siri and Microsoft Cortana are giving students a chance to interact with educational material without the interaction with the teacher. Arizona State University gives many of its incoming students an Amazon Alexa which will give them information about their campus needs

Personalization

The understanding level and grasping power of each student is different. Traditional teaching techniques fail to cater to a student's individual needs. This is where AI agents help the underlying Machine Learning algorithms in these systems to identify trends and patterns in the student learning data and produce educational insight. These AI systems craft individual mini-curriculum for students with diverse interests in various subjects and varied abilities. In Washington Leadership Academy students learn via personalized academics and indulge in real-world practice while utilizing leading technologies. The academy develops materials, curriculum, and lessons that are shared openly to foster further adoption and innovation. Reinforcement Learning has been used to design a tutoring system by Stanford University and the University of Washington to deliver effective learning solutions. Another organization Whizz Education primarily develops adaptive mathematics curriculum claims that if a student spends an hour per week with their AI-powered tutor during an academic year, it can augment a student's learning rate by 18 months in comparison to the student's peers. Bill Gates via his foundation Bill & Melinda Gates has been backing their personalised education and has already invested \$120 million. Tutoring apps customize their lesson structures depending on the students' performance. Toppr a learning app in the Indian Education space is utilizing best practices in AI to map out a student's strengths and weaknesses and takes into consideration individual learning speeds and ensures that students remain motivated. India has launched 'Operation Digital Board' which aims to incorporate techniques like adaptive learning and intelligent tutoring by using AI.

Grading and Assessment

Machines are grading multiple-choice tests; they are very close to being able to correct subjective questions also. Educational robots or automated evaluation systems can be

used to assess grading assignments and tests. Pearson's Write to Learn and Turnitin's Light side can score essays and detect plagiarism. The robots can give a quick, accurate and fair assessment and provides students with timely feedback which can be used to improve future performance.

Remote Proctoring is a new technology which uses the web camera to invigilate students who are giving the exam from any classroom/home. The onscreen evaluation system adopted by many Universities is an intelligent system that auto-calculates the marks and also verifies whether the examiner has checked all the pages or not. Bots are used to assess subjective answers given by the students in GRE test administered by ETS (ETS, 2018). Earlier the narrative answers were being assessed by two human experts to reduce the possibility of any error whereas now, ETS has replaced one of the two experts by a bot.

Supervised classification models to reduce drop-out rates

Teachers can identify students with high possibility of dropping out and thereby help them through Remote learning systems and smart classrooms. In 2015 Andhra Pradesh Government partnered with Microsoft to handle the problem of school dropouts. By using Microsoft's Azure machine learning platform, an application was developed, which is predicting which students are most likely to drop out of school. More than 10,000 schools in Andhra Pradesh are using this app. It processes complex data sets that include details about enrolment, student performance, school infrastructure and socio-economic demographics to find predictive patterns. With these data administrators and educators can intervene and prevent dropouts and empower them to finish their education and graduate, join the work that will help grow the economy of the country.

Benefits

In India, a considerable number of learners reside in remote areas and cannot attend proper educational institutions because of distance, lack of transportation and financial problems. There exists a digital divide between urban and rural populations. AI in Education can transform this digital divide into digital opportunity by catering to the needs of everyone wherever they are in an affordable way. Various tutoring programs and learning applications with skill development are being deployed all over the world. AI-based systems will bring the classroom at one's fingertips. It not only educates but enhances the skills of students and working professionals to be ready for future challenges. It will also help teachers and educators keep track of the latest developments.

Conclusion

Humans can benefit greatly from AI systems as they cost-efficient and can save time and energy. The use of AI assisted tools should not be viewed as a replacement for humans instead their adoption in different areas can relieve humans from repetitive, monotonous tasks. It has the potential to transform human lives, the way people work, through its enormous computing power and speed. To leverage the benefits of a technology like AI, the government has to support partnerships with private organizations and provide access to infrastructure and funding for research. One of the main reliance of AI is on the data for it to learn and make informed decisions the task of making this data available is enormous, and the government must ensure that the privacy of the individual, student and organization is preserved. There is a lot of anonymity in how the AI arrives at a decision once it learns to solve a task, so much needs to be learnt about the inherent mechanisms of these systems. Also, there is no guarantee that AI can fully carry out its tasks without human supervision, so we can view AI has a human assistant for few years at least.

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